

Handbook on Best Practices for Accessing Data through Firm Collaborations

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Abstract

Firm data collaborations offer unique opportunities to answer novel, policy-relevant research questions that cannot be addressed using traditional data sources. This handbook provides practical guidance for researchers seeking to access and use firm-generated data, drawing on first-hand experience and insights from structured interviews. It outlines the key steps of establishing and managing data collaborations between researchers and firms, from initiating contact to building long-term partnerships. The report addresses organizational, legal and methodological challenges, highlights the role of Research Data Centers, and provides advice for building trust-based, mutually beneficial collaborations. Designed for applied social scientists, the handbook helps assess whether such collaborations are a good fit, and how to make them work in practice.

Keywords: firm data, data access, data collaborations, industry-academia collaborations

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1. Introduction

Collaborations between academia and industry have long been recognized as a powerful driver of innovation, enabling technological progress, product development, and economic growth. Traditionally, such partnerships have been most visible in fields like engineering, life sciences, and information technology, where joint research and development (R&D), technology transfer, and applied research are common. Governments around the world actively encourage these engagements, viewing them as an important mechanism for translating scientific knowledge into practical applications that benefit both firms and society at large. In Germany, various initiatives, from funding schemes by the German Research Foundation (DFG) to the Stifterverband's "Industry Engagement" programs, have sought to foster and institutionalize such cooperation.

In recent years, however, a new and less conventional form of collaboration has gained importance: partnerships between firms and social scientists built around access to firm-generated data. Unlike conventional R&D collaborations, these partnerships do not aim to develop a tangible product or technology. Instead, they focus on unlocking the potential of high-frequency, fine-grained, and often highly proprietary datasets collected in the course of business operations. For researchers in economics and the broader social sciences, such data can provide unprecedented insights into economic and societal dynamics, inform evidence-based policy advice, and support research questions that cannot be answered using traditional data sources such as surveys or administrative records.

The growing interest in firm data collaborations reflects broader changes in both academia and industry. On the academic side, researchers increasingly require timely, granular, and large-scale data to study complex phenomena, from market dynamics to consumer behavior and labor market transitions. On the industry side, more firms have professionalized their data collection and analysis, establishing in-house data science teams and recognizing the strategic value of their data assets. These developments create opportunities for mutually beneficial exchange: firms can benefit from cutting-edge analytical expertise, independent evaluation, and reputational gains, while researchers gain access to unique data and institutional knowledge that enrich both academic work and policy relevance.

A growing body of empirical work illustrates the breadth and impact of research enabled by such collaborations. For example, Coey, Larsen, and Platt (2020) analyze consumer search behavior using transaction-level data from an online platform; Hortaçsu, Natan, Parsley, Schweg, and Williams (2024) study organizational structure and pricing strategies in the airline industry; Farronato and Fradkin (2022) assess the welfare effects of Airbnb's market entry on

the accommodation sector; Carlin, Olafsson, and Pagel (2023) use individual-level transaction data from a financial aggregation platform to analyze how technology adoption impacts consumer financial decision making; and Azar, Huet-Vaughn, Marinescu, Taska, and von Wachter (2024) investigate the interaction between minimum wage policies and labor market concentration using detailed vacancy data. These studies underscore the diversity of economic questions that can be addressed when firm-generated data is made available for research.²

However, such collaborations remain the exception rather than the norm, particularly in Germany and Europe. Despite their potential, firm data are rarely made available for external research due to concerns over confidentiality, privacy, and the protection of business secrets. Legal frameworks such as the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) impose high standards for data processing and limit use cases for which informed consent was not obtained. Moreover, some firms may view their data as a commercial asset to be monetized, while others may fear reputational risks or competitive disadvantages from external analysis. Even when firms are open to collaboration, practical hurdles can arise: internal data may be fragmented,

Box 1. Successful Firm Collaborations at FDZ Ruhr (RWI)

The FDZ Ruhr, RWI's Research Data Center, has developed a strong track record in partnering with companies to make operational data available for research. At the core of these collaborations lies a clear principle: all projects are designed to enable rigorous, transparent data access for researchers beyond RWI. The goal is not merely to support internal analysis, but to expand the empirical foundation for the broader academic community. To achieve this, the RDC leverages its expertise in data documentation, preparation, and access management according to the FAIR principles.² By combining institutional credibility with secure infrastructure and legal know-how, the FDZ Ruhr has successfully created sustainable models of collaboration in which firm-generated data are made accessible for independent scientific use.

Notable partnerships

- **Immobilien Scout GmbH***: housing market data
- **microm Micromarketing-Systeme und Consult GmbH****: granular spatial socio-economic data

In cooperation with the named partners, the FDZ Ruhr can provide access to these datasets for scientific purposes to every researcher.

* DOI: 10.7807/immo:redx:suf:v14.1

** DOI: 10.7807/microm:suf:v14

² Broader overviews of the use of privately held data for economic research and economic statistics can be found in Abraham et al. (2022), Chetty et al. (2024), Einav & Levin (2014) and Vavra (2021).

² The FAIR principles are guidelines to foster the **F**indability, **A**ccessibility, **I**nteroperability, and **R**euse of digital assets and are a fundamental cornerstone for the work of RDCs (<https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>).

undocumented, or difficult to harmonize, and the costs of preparing it for external use may be underestimated.

Compared to engineering-focused collaborations, the “win-win” in firm data partnerships can be more difficult to communicate and to achieve. In traditional R&D, mutual benefits are often concrete and immediate. In contrast, the value of a social science research project may be harder for firms to quantify, especially when benefits are indirect or long-term. Researchers, for their part, must navigate institutional obligations regarding transparency, replicability, and academic independence, requirements that can sometimes clash with firms’ expectations for confidentiality and control. The challenge, therefore, lies in finding common ground and establishing trust while designing agreements that satisfy both parties’ objectives and constraints.

Against this backdrop, this handbook offers practical guidance for social scientists seeking to establish and sustain data collaborations with firms for research purposes. While the focus is on the social sciences, particularly economics, the principles and insights discussed here are relevant to other disciplines where firm-generated data can provide valuable empirical leverage. The handbook aims to:

- Outline the benefits and challenges of firm data collaborations from both the researcher’s and the firm’s perspective,
- Provide step-by-step advice for initiating, negotiating, and managing such partnerships,
- Offer strategies for ensuring that collaborations yield scientifically rigorous, policy-relevant, and mutually beneficial outcomes,
- Highlight the role of Research Data Centers (RDCs) as trusted intermediaries.

This report builds on hands-on experience from data collaborations at RWI–Leibniz Institute for Economic Research and at the ifo Institute, where RDCs have played a central role in enabling secure and sustainable access to firm data (see **Box 1** and **Box 2**). We complement this with insights from structured interviews with both researchers and firms, as well as lessons from established institutions to reflect the diversity of paths toward successful collaboration. In doing so, we seek to address a current gap in practical guidance for researchers navigating such partnerships.

Our goal is not to advocate for firm data collaborations at all costs, but to help researchers assess whether such a partnership is suitable for their project, and if so, to approach it strategically. We also aim to provide insights for firms, clarifying the incentives and working methods of researchers and illustrating how collaboration can serve both business objectives and the public good.

Ultimately, firm data collaborations represent an underutilized opportunity to enhance both scientific inquiry and societal impact. When designed and managed well, they can bridge the gap between academic rigor and real-world relevance, producing research that not only advances theory but also informs decision-making in policy and practice. The following chapters offer a roadmap for navigating this complex yet promising landscape.

Box 2. Successful Firm Collaborations at the ifo Institute

ifo's experience with accessing firm data dates back to 1949, building a long tradition of conducting firm surveys. Participating companies benefit from micro-aggregated results relevant for their firm, as well as insights into industry trends and competitor development that are specifically provided for their firm. This mutually beneficial model has supported long-standing data collaborations.

From Surveys to Direct Data Collaborations

Since 2019, ifo has pursued a strategy of building direct data collaborations with firms, enabling access to valuable and novel datasets within its internal research network. This approach aligns with the institute's broader goal of harnessing Big Data for research and policy advice. These initiatives have allowed the institute to develop substantial expertise in establishing and managing such collaborations, while navigating the challenges that often limit open data sharing.

Notable partnerships

- **Mastercard**^{*}: anonymized credit card transaction data at granular geographical level
- **N26**^{**}: anonymized bank account data
- **Colliers**^{***}: anonymized corporate real-estate data

* See e.g., Alipour et al. (2024): Working from Home and Consumption in Cities

** See e.g., Falck et al. (2025): How Consumers have Managed the Multicrisis

*** See e.g., Krause et al. (2024): The Impact of Working from Home on the German Office Real Estate Market

2. The Win-Win Situation: Benefits & Challenges of Data Collaborations

Academic-industry collaborations should be framed as a “win-win” situation, where both researchers and firms derive meaningful value from the exchange. What constitutes a win for each side depends heavily on the nature of the collaboration. In applied R&D settings, mutual benefit tends to be more clearly defined, such as through prototypes, patent applications, or product/service development. In contrast, for data collaborations in the realm of social sciences, the value proposition can be less obvious and highly context-dependent. What one party sees as an opportunity, the other may perceive as a risk. Therefore, while researchers aim to tackle novel research questions with firm data, firms may find it hard to understand how the academic value of a research project outweighs the risk of sharing internal information with external partners.

The scope, perceived value, and associated risk of firm data collaborations can vary significantly depending on the research question, research design, the firm’s internal structure and incentives, and the academic institutional constraints. The ability to identify and articulate a compelling win-win proposition, tailored to the specificities of the setting, is one of the most important elements in establishing a successful collaboration.

Drawing on insights from first-hand experiences and structured interviews with both researchers and firms, this section explores both the benefits and challenges of such collaborations. We begin by examining the researcher’s perspective, followed by that of the firm.

2.1. The Researcher Perspective

From the researchers’ perspective, firm collaborations can offer substantial benefits, particularly when it comes to accessing novel data, exploring original research questions, and gaining institutional insights. At the same time, these collaborations come with significant challenges, ranging from legal and procedural complexities, misaligned timelines and uncertainty about project initiation or completion.

2.1.1. Benefits

Novel data

Firm collaborations can offer access to novel datasets, enabling researchers to pursue questions that would be difficult, if not impossible to address using conventional data sources like surveys or administrative data. Firm data can be either more granular, more frequent, or otherwise unavailable through public or other proprietary sources. For example, researchers may obtain personnel data from internal HR systems, transaction-level financial data, platform usage logs, detailed sales information, or experimental data from randomized control trials implemented within firms. The versatility of such data creates opportunities for researchers in nearly all social science subfields to publish their work. This level of detail not only opens up

new empirical research avenues but also allows for the implementation of more rigorous research designs. Access to fine-grained firm data can facilitate causal inference, yielding results that are both academically robust and highly relevant for policy design and, if applicable, firm decision-making.

Impactful Research

At the same time, researchers are able to pursue more original and impactful research questions, which can lead to stronger contributions to academic literature and, in turn, shape their career trajectory given an increased probability of publication in top-tier journals. Interviewees emphasized that engaging with real-world data frequently results in work that is both innovative and policy-relevant, increasing their motivation to pursue such collaborations. For instance, organizational economists among our interviewees noted that firms' willingness to engage in randomization opened opportunities to test mechanisms in ways rarely feasible through other channels.

Institutional Knowledge

In addition to empirical and publication-related gains, firm collaborations offer access to first-hand institutional knowledge and operational context. Through ongoing interactions with firm partners, researchers deepen their understanding of internal processes, industry dynamics, and the practical meaning behind the data. This knowledge can be invaluable for designing empirical strategies, interpreting results, and formulating implications that are grounded in institutional reality. Additionally, it helps to identify novel research questions with practical implications.

2.1.2. Challenges

While collaborations can offer substantial benefits, they also come with a number of organizational, legal and technical challenges that researchers need to be prepared to navigate.

Internal Coordination and Organizational Barriers

Successful firm collaborations depend not only on the willingness of a firm to share data, but also on effective coordination among multiple internal stakeholders. For a collaboration to move forward a legal team typically needs to assess contractual and data privacy risks; a data team needs to prepare the data, provide access, and clarify content; senior leadership would need to endorse the collaboration strategically. This internal alignment can be difficult to achieve and may turn into a lengthy process, especially with firms that lack established procedures for working with external researchers. This presents a major challenge for researchers since they often have limited visibility into the internal processes of the firm and have no influence over how quickly firm partners align internally. Institutional complexity is difficult to navigate, especially when considering tight deadlines and academic timelines.

One important challenge is to find an *internal champion*, a person holding a sufficiently senior position to advocate for the collaboration and escalate it internally, while also being directly involved in the project and able to drive it forward. Having a contact who is personally interested in academic research or data-driven analysis can also be a major advantage, as they are more likely to understand the potential value of the project and stay engaged throughout its development. Without such a champion, the project can be delayed in bureaucratic processes and fail to gain traction beyond the exploratory phase.

Interviewees also mentioned that employee turnover on the firm side is a common reason why collaborations are delayed, disrupted, or ultimately abandoned. Changes in team composition, especially when a supportive contact leaves, can be detrimental to the successful completion of the project and can lead to a shift in priorities. A new manager may deprioritize the project, fail to recognize its relevance, or be unwilling to invest the necessary time and resources. To mitigate this risk, maintaining regular contact and building relationships with multiple stakeholders inside the firm can be an effective strategy.

Moreover, the difference in working timelines and expectations between firms and researchers often becomes a challenge. Firms often expect fast results and may not anticipate the lengthy and iterative nature of academic research. Researchers, by contrast, work under the pressure of producing high-quality, peer-reviewed publications, often over the course of many months or even years. These diverging timelines can create tension, and even disengagement by the firm. To mitigate such risks, it is important to maintain momentum, establish realistic milestones, offer interim updates, and communicate openly about academic deliverables and timing constraints from the outset.

Legal and Data Protection Concerns

Legal and data protection considerations are among the most frequent challenges in setting up data-based collaborations with firms. These often stem from a fundamental misalignment between academic requirements, such as transparency, replicability, and long-term data retention, and firms' expectations regarding confidentiality, control and legal risk management. Negotiating this space requires early and clear communication, as well as a willingness to compromise on both sides. Researchers are therefore advised to engage proactively and carefully with contractual matters, as they may have significant implications for data access, publication rights, and the overall viability of their projects.

To protect the integrity of their research, researchers should ensure that their academic obligations are not compromised by overly restrictive agreements, especially with respect to data retention and replicability. Good scientific practice often requires that data be preserved for at least ten years, and many journals mandate that underlying data be available for replication.³ However, some firms may only be willing to share data under the condition that it

³ For more information, consult the German Research Foundation Code of Conduct (see <https://www.dfg.de/en/basics-topics/basics-and-principles-of-funding/good-research-practice/code-of-conduct>).

be permanently deleted after the project ends or may object to any form of external storage. In such cases, it is essential to clarify early on the expected project timelines, the requirements imposed by academic publication standards and to jointly explore solutions that satisfy both parties.

Moreover, in some cases, firms may be reluctant to allow the data to be used beyond the original project scope or may require reviewing results before publication. Such restrictions can raise concerns about academic independence and publication freedom. Researchers should be prepared to address these issues early in the negotiation process, ideally with institutional support, such as a data protection officer or experienced RDC staff, and pre-defined publication safeguards that align with academic norms.

Due to firms' general data security concerns, it is vital that transparency in data usage is guaranteed. Firms often want to know who will access the data, where it will be stored, what protections will be in place, and how potential misuse will be prevented. Building trust depends in part on researchers being able to provide concrete answers to these questions, including outlining infrastructure, data access procedure, and confidentiality safeguards. Interviewees highlighted that clearly communicating these details early in the collaboration can reduce friction with legal departments and data protection officers, especially in firms with limited prior experience in research partnerships.

Data Sharing and Usability

Even when research interests are aligned and clarified, data access and usability can pose substantial challenges for the success of a collaboration. In many cases, firms do not systematically collect, store, or harmonize their datasets in formats that are readily usable for research. Data can be fragmented across departments and platforms, lack standardization that facilitates merging, and be poorly documented or have missing metadata. Firms that lack centralized data governance structures may initially underestimate the internal resources required and implicit costs of a data collaboration. Interviewees highlighted that companies may be unaware of the full scope or the value of their own data, and it may not be clear who is responsible for data pre-processing, extraction or delivery.

These limitations can make cross-departmental coordination difficult and time-consuming. What initially seemed feasible may turn out to be more resource-intensive than expected, leading some firms to reassess and ultimately withdraw from the collaboration. Such situations are especially challenging for junior researchers working under strict academic timelines. Even when collaborations proceed, the coordination effort often entails delays and multiple rounds of clarification to fully understand the data-generating process and ensure data quality.

In addition, many firms lack established procedures for sharing data with external partners, which often means that researchers may face long approval chains and legal bottlenecks, adding an additional layer of potential delays. Even after contracts are signed, it may take months to receive the data, especially in organizations where responsibilities are diffused or where internal priorities shift frequently.

Firms may impose limitations on how the data can be used, e.g. by limiting usage to a single project or a narrow research question. Researchers may find it difficult to negotiate extensions for follow-up projects, especially when internal firm priorities or staff have changed. Additionally, firms may not be ready to disclose all needed information about the data generating process, while researchers need to assess the quality and representativity of the data received. These limitations highlight the importance of early and transparent conversations about the intended scope of data use, potential reuse and the completeness of the available data.

2.2. The Firm Perspective

Firms may produce data with significant potential for high-quality research. However, building the internal structures and capabilities required to collect and analyze such data can be costly. This raises the question of why firms should engage in data collaborations with researchers, what they stand to gain, and what challenges they may face during the process.

2.2.1. Benefits

Strategic Use of Existing Data

Recent developments indicate that data analytics is playing an increasingly central role in strategic decision-making, yet much potential remains untapped. Some firms are only beginning to realize the value of their data, while others have already embedded data collection into core processes. A survey carried out on behalf of the European Commission (2022) reveals that among the 10,006 surveyed enterprises in the EU27, 95% store data from at least one source, mainly stemming from business processes, customers, information systems, and business data. 79% of the enterprises who store data also analyze it, with varying frequency. For firms that already collect operational data, sharing it with researchers may entail minimal additional effort, especially if the data is well structured and documented. Academic use of firm data may also signal high data quality, particularly relevant for firms that commercialize their data or build data-driven products and services. In some cases, data collaborations may even result in commercial data products or produce research findings that directly inform business improvements.

Enhancing Internal Data Practices and Talent Acquisition

Sharing data with researchers can offer indirect but significant organizational benefits. As firms move toward a more professionalized use of data, they may face challenges in recruiting skilled personnel. Data collaborations provide an opportunity to engage with highly trained researchers who can apply advanced analytical methods to (firm) data. In exchange for access, researchers may offer support in data curation, documentation, or even model development (e.g., firms' text mining model about customer satisfaction). Such collaborations can trigger internal learning processes, improve data quality, and foster a culture of data awareness. Moreover, collaboration with academic institutions can enhance a firm's employer branding,

particularly among purpose-driven employees from younger generations, who value working for organizations that contribute to the public good.

Reputational Gains and Public Visibility

Joint policy publications, reports, or public events resulting from data collaborations can enhance a firm's visibility and credibility, showcasing transparency and social engagement. These outputs can improve the firm's public image, help attract new partners and serve as signals of innovation. Firms may also benefit from being cited in academic research, further embedding their presence in the scientific community. Such collaborations can also align with Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) strategies. Supporting research for the public good, sometimes framed as "Data for Good" initiatives, can bolster a firm's ethical reputation and potentially preempt more stringent regulatory scrutiny.

2.2.2. Challenges

Building Trust and Mutual Understanding

Beyond practical issues that may arise when initiating a data collaboration, the foremost challenge lies in establishing mutual understanding and trust between firms and researchers. Employees and researchers often come from fundamentally different backgrounds, using distinct terminology and pursuing divergent objectives. Firms may fear losing control over sensitive data once it is shared or giving away strategic information to competitors.

Furthermore, the slow pace and unfamiliar conventions of academic publishing can create frustration and doubt about the value of the collaboration. Academic projects may appear opaque or inefficient, particularly when firms are used to fast development cycles, and may expect quick and PR-friendly results. Requirements such as data archiving for replication purposes may be perceived as risky.

Transparent communication of intentions, expectations, and timelines is therefore essential. Research Data Centers can play a valuable role here: not only do they offer secure infrastructure and expertise in handling sensitive data, but they can also serve as intermediaries or trusted third parties, reducing the perceived risks of data sharing and lowering the coordination burden.

Resource Constraints

Providing data for research purposes can strain a firm's resources. The complexity of such a task depends on the nature of the data and how data collection processes are structured within the firm. If data is dispersed across departments, coordination becomes more time-consuming. Internally aligning and externally coordinating with researchers requires time and personnel, resources that may be in short supply. Even if departments are willing to collaborate, they are often required to evaluate the viability and scalability of their operations. While contributing to academic research may be desirable for many reasons, firms may often find it difficult to

quantify the return on their investments. This challenge may be especially acute for firms that do not see immediate or strategic value in such an engagement.

Legal, Privacy, and Compliance Concerns

Firms are bound by data protection laws and internal compliance standards. Sharing data may raise concerns about legal risks or inadvertent disclosure of sensitive business information. Even when data sharing is legally permissible, firms may fear exposing proprietary processes or competitive advantages. Depending on the area of data collection, particularly when employees are involved, firms may be required to integrate the perspectives of additional units, such as workers' councils. Addressing these concerns requires legal consultation, which in turn adds to the cost of collaboration.

2.3. Finding the Common Ground

As discussed in the previous sections collaborating with firms can open up valuable research opportunities, enabling access to unique data, practical insights, and real-world problems that are otherwise difficult to study. At the same time, such partnerships require effort, mutual understanding, and a clear articulation of benefits on both sides.

The key to a successful collaboration lies in identifying and clearly communicating the win-win potential. Researchers should be ready to explain their project in accessible terms, define exactly what data is needed and why, and proactively highlight the mutual value. Non-disclosure agreements can help address confidentiality concerns early on. Sometimes, compromise is necessary. For instance, working with older data can still provide meaningful insights while easing firms' worries about sensitive information. However, access to older data could be a problem for the firm due to higher cost making the data accessible.

Ultimately, understanding each other's goals, timelines and constraints is essential. Being able to "pitch the win-win" clearly is one of the most important skills researchers can develop when working with industry partners. The next chapter will provide hands-on guidance for initiating and structuring such collaborations.

3. How Do Collaborations Work in Practice?

The process of planning, establishing, and maintaining firm data collaborations is similar to a prototypical data lifecycle: from the initial idea to first contact, implementation, publication, follow-up, handover, and structured exit, as illustrated in [Figure 1](#). It involves multiple, sometimes overlapping stages. Additionally, it is not a unidirectional process but sometimes requires a back-and-forth between stages due to changing concepts, staff turnover, unrealistic demands, or data problems. In some cases, ending a collaboration (attempt) at any stage might be the best outcome.

FINDING THE **WIN-WIN**: NAVIGATING THE PATH OF COLLABORATION

BEFORE CONTACTING FIRMS

- Develop a clear research idea and data vision, seek feedback from experts.
- Build a capable team and secure support from institutional infrastructure.
- Manage expectations, assess risks, and firm prospects.

FROM FIRST CONTACT TO PARTNERSHIP

- Target the right decision-makers with a tailored outreach.
- Present a compelling pitch of your broad research idea to spark interest.
- Identify common ground and define a win-win basis for collaboration.
- Agree on clear next steps and maintain momentum.

LEGAL AND OPERATIONAL CONSIDERATIONS

- Define objectives, roles, and timelines.
- Establish a formal collaboration agreement covering data usage and security.
- Set up data management process and responsibilities to ensure quality, transparency and reproducibility.

MANAGING THE COLLABORATION OVER TIME

- Align on (long-term) goals and benefits.
- Maintain regular communication and coordination.
- Develop clear handover processes to secure knowledge transfer and guarantee continuity if project members leave.

ENDING THE COLLABORATION

- Agree on orderly handover of data and rights.
- Consider contractual provisions for a structured exit.
- Ensure confidentiality and conduct a joint review.

Figure 1. Navigating the Path of Collaboration

The following subsections provide advice for each stage of the process. Careful planning and awareness of each stage are essential, especially when steps are skipped. Not every piece of advice or stage mentioned here might fit every collaboration due to different scopes, goals, complexity, timelines and participants. However, the specific *do's* and *don'ts* highlighted at the end of each subsection aim to guide researchers approach each stage more effectively.

3.1. Before Contacting Firms

Development of research idea(s)

Before approaching a firm, researchers should develop a clear project idea that defines the research question, contribution, and need for collaboration. Even if contacted by a firm, it is crucial to prepare thoroughly before meeting. Junior researchers especially benefit from guidance by senior colleagues, who can identify blind spots, refine concepts, and share insights from past collaborations. Their experience, feedback, and resources help ensure academic rigor and feasibility. Presenting early ideas in internal seminars - ideally multiple times - further improves quality. The risk of idea theft is minimal, while constructive feedback helps refine promising projects and discard weak ones early.

Forming a research team and finding institutional support

Finding researchers who have more experience with firm data collaborations and teaming up with them can be a good idea. For junior researchers having a co-author on a similar hierarchy and experience level can help to share daily research tasks and manage demanding collaborations with tight deadlines.

Additionally, researchers should seek early advice and support from infrastructure or service units at their institution (if they exist). This includes first thinking about potential legal and ethical questions related to the potential research design and the firm data involved. Talk informally to an Institutional Review Board (IRB) and a data protection officer about potential pitfalls.⁴ Other stakeholders to be contacted might include an RDC, data stewards or IT department for research data infrastructure-related questions (e.g., secure storage/computation or research data management standards) or the head of the research unit for funding opportunities.

Ideal setting, flexibility and feasibility

A key part of early planning is envisioning what the ideal but real-world data setup would look like. What information is required to answer the research question? At what level of detail? Over what time span? Who would be an ideal firm partner and how long would it take to generate meaningful results? Thinking through this ideal scenario helps clarify what to ask for, but it is just as important to anticipate areas where researchers are willing to compromise without making the analysis impossible.

⁴ For more info on research ethics and approvals see RatSWD collection Best Practices for Research Ethics (see <https://www.konsortswd.de/en/topics/best-practices-research-ethics/>).

At this stage, researchers often do not know yet what kind of firm data will actually be usable. There is a high chance that the final research project will look different than originally planned or imagined. It is therefore good practice to remain flexible and have an alternative research question or design in mind.

In general, firms may have commercial, legal or reputational concerns, other interests or internal limitations on data access and processing which limit the scope of potential research questions. For example, it might not be in the interest of social media platforms to investigate their potential harm to the mental health of its users. On the other hand, researchers should avoid choosing pleasing topics with predetermined or expected results by the firm just to get data. While it is ok to agree on a broad research topic with the firm, researchers must be able to perform their analysis independently and transparently. Phrased differently, publication of results must not depend on whether the results are favorable or dangerous for the firm or not.⁵

Expectation and risk management

Most outreach attempts to firms never progress. Many researchers report that initial contact is often met with silence or outright rejection. Considering the firm's perspective early, whether the research question is relevant and why the firm should collaborate is therefore essential.

It can be useful to approach several firms in parallel, as this increases the likelihood of success. However, researchers rarely have the capacity to manage multiple collaborations at once, especially at the start. Ending a contact opportunistically because a "better" firm is found is poor practice, and abandoning established contacts without communication is unacceptable, reflecting badly on the researcher, the institution and science in general.

Even successful collaborations often face long timelines, internal approvals, legal checks, and unexpected delays. For researchers with strict time limits, especially (advanced) PhD students and postdocs, this unpredictability is risky. Projects may stall or collapse beyond the researcher's control. To mitigate this, researchers should assess timelines carefully, consider fallback projects using public data, and discuss these risks with supervisors or mentors from the outset.

⁵ In general, the rules of good scientific practice (<https://wissenschaftliche-integritaet.de/en/>) and guidelines on providing scientific advice (https://www.leibniz-gemeinschaft.de/fileadmin/documents/1128-2622/Leibniz_Guidelines_on_Providing_Scientific_Advice_to_Policymakers_and_Society.pdf) apply to firm data collaborations as well.

Before Contacting Firms

What to do

- Define a clear research idea
 - Seek feedback and advice early
 - Explore institutional support
 - Sketch the ideal data scenario
 - Consider feasibility of potential results
 - Plan for flexibility
 - Evaluate risks and timelines
 - Develop an outreach strategy
 - Have a plan B
 - Think about how to ensure research independence
-

What NOT to do

- Approach firms with vague ideas
- Avoid seeking feedback and advice
- Ignore or abandon contacts unannounced
- Be overly rigid in your approach

3.2. From First Contact to Partnership: How to Get Started

Initiating Contact

The first step in establishing a successful firm collaboration often begins with developing a well thought-through outreach strategy. Ideally, the initial contact should come from a senior researcher with prior experience in firm collaborations. This signals not only credibility, but also the ability to deliver a project that aligns with the firm's interests. Several researchers have emphasized that academic reputation, seniority and experience with industry partnerships can make a difference and facilitate access to key decision-makers within the firm.

The success of the outreach often hinges on who receives the initial email. Choosing the right contact is therefore a strategic decision. Whenever possible, researchers should reach out to individuals as high as possible in the firm's organizational hierarchy, namely those with the authority to either make or advocate for collaboration decisions.

In smaller firms, reaching out directly to the CEO or other C-level executives (i.e. top senior managers, such as CTO, COO, CFO) is often possible and effective, especially when the organization has fewer internal layers. In larger firms, the executive team is usually less accessible. In such cases, targeting senior leadership just below the C-level, such as Vice-Presidents or Heads of Units is often more realistic. These individuals typically lead major business functions, have the needed operational insight and would be able to assess the potential value of the collaboration and escalate the proposal internally. An alternative strategy could be to reach out to the Public Relations department, which is often well connected within a company.

In parallel, identifying an internal champion early in the process can greatly improve the likelihood of success. This person, often active more on the operational side, would be researchers' main point of contact and internal advocate. They are typically directly interested in the research topic, willing to invest time and able to bridge communication between the academic and corporate stakeholders. A great champion not only pushes the collaboration forward but also helps navigate internal processes and ensures engagement from the other involved departments.

The initial email should be concise, professional and tailored to the firm's context. Key elements to include are:

- A brief summary of the research idea and why it is relevant for the firm
- A clear statement of interest in exploring a collaboration
- An invitation for a short call or meeting
- Optional: a concise business-oriented slide deck (max. 3 slides) pitching the idea and highlighting the potential value of the collaboration.

Researchers should avoid writing a detailed breakdown of the research agenda, overly technical language, or detailed data requirements. The goal is to spark an interest and secure a meeting, and not to finalize a collaboration from the first interaction. Insights from experienced researchers suggest that describing the research idea broadly helps to signal openness and flexibility, giving the firm the space to express their own interests into the topic.

First Meeting

Once initial contact has been established and a meeting is set, preparing a compelling pitch becomes the next crucial step. The goal of the first meeting is to spark interest, signal expertise, initiate a conversation about the feasibility of collaborating, brainstorm about common interests, and clarify the research process. When leaving this meeting, the firm should have a clear understanding of the potential value the collaboration could offer. Interviewees consistently highlighted the importance of identifying a win-win scenario from the first pitch.

Rather than leading with a fully specified and set research agenda, researchers should present a broad framing of the research idea, outlining the general question they are interested in, its relevance not only for society at large, but also for the targeted company. One should think of this initial meeting as an opportunity to collaborate. Flexibility at this stage is important. Researchers may consider integrating adjacent analyses that align with the company's interests, even if these fall outside the direct scope of the future academic article. This approach could

From First Contact to Partnership

What to do

- Target individuals with decision-making power for the first contact
- Make first contact through a senior researcher (reputation matters)
- Thoroughly prepare pitch of (broad) research idea
- Use first meeting to explore common interests
- Highlight the win-win early on
- Find an internal champion
- Be flexible
- Highlight prior experience (if available)
- Explain academic timelines, expectations, importance of academic freedom
- Be prepared to talk about your data needs
- Explain clearly how you will handle the data
- Conclude first meeting with next steps

What NOT to do

- Contact low-level employees or in unrelated departments
- Overload your outreach email
- Expect firms to understand academic jargon
- Pitch an entire research agenda
- Underestimate the importance of firm priorities
- Be afraid to ask about the firm's priorities
- Treat the first meeting as a contract negotiation
- Be afraid to ask for what you need
- Overcommit early
- Be rigid in approaching the collaboration
- Be afraid to ask questions about processes within the firm
- Present academic work as a consulting project

act as a bargaining tool, a way to build trust and ultimately, gain institutional insights. It also offers an opportunity to learn more about the operations of the firm, which may not only help refine the research design, but also allow researchers to better understand the firm's priorities.

If applicable, a first pitch should also mention prior experience with firm collaborations. This may include outlining the nature of the collaboration, the ability to manage procedural complexity, to ensure data security, and deliver results within agreed timelines. Where possible, it is useful to highlight the benefits other partner firms derived from the collaboration, such as actionable insights, internal impact or, where relevant, successful integration of research findings into decision-making processes.

Since many firms may be unfamiliar with how academic research is conducted, the first meeting is also an opportunity to manage expectations. Because in most cases corporate timelines do not align with academic ones, researchers should briefly explain what an academic timeline looks like, what a publication lag entails, highlight the trade-off between speed and rigor, and what the phases of the collaboration might entail. Several researchers and interviewed firms noted that different working speeds can become a source of frustration unless clarified early. At the same time, researchers may want to emphasize their analytical and methodological expertise, while distinguishing the goals of academic research from those of consulting work.

In a first meeting researchers should be able to specify what types of data are needed, why and how the data will be used to answer the research question. An ideal outcome of the meeting would be to gain an understanding of the firm's available data, how costly it would be to retrieve or process it, what structure the data would have. This would not only help the researcher get an understanding of the potential duration of the project, but also the firm in assessing the implicit effort required and the feasibility of the collaboration. In fact, having an early understanding of the data is instrumental in assessing whether the potential of the collaboration, therefore researchers should aim to get in touch with an operational employee with data access responsibilities who could clarify questions. Additionally, the first meeting should also address data security and confidentiality, data management and storage. Highlighting successful setups in prior collaborations would be useful to illustrate this point.

Finally, the meeting should end with clarity on next steps: either agreeing to provide more detailed information, scheduling a follow-up meeting, or allowing time for internal discussion and further brainstorming. At this exploratory stage, establishing momentum and showing initiative is crucial. Researchers are advised to be proactive and make concrete suggestions on how to proceed. Providing a brief summary of the key discussion points agreed action points (deliverables) can help maintain engagement and facilitate a smooth transition into the next phase.

3.3. Early Stages of the Collaboration: Legal and Operational Considerations

Operational Aspects

After a successful first meeting, the next step is to bring the collaboration into action and to work on the agreed action points (deliverables). This includes further brainstorming to refine the exact research questions, identifying potential additional deliverables (e.g., common publication / policy paper), and clarifying the full scope of the collaboration. Managing expectations from the outset is critical, particularly concerning the availability, format, and timelines of data delivery.

Structured processes and clear communication channels should be established, with defined responsibilities and roles within the project team. Maintaining regular contact, providing updates, and ensuring transparency were consistently highlighted in the interviews as best practices. While identifying an internal champion remains critical, it can be equally valuable to build a broader network within the company. Engaging with multiple stakeholders not only helps access relevant internal knowledge and expertise throughout the collaboration, but can

Early Stages of the Collaboration

What to do

- Clarify and align expectations
- Negotiate legal clauses carefully
- Clarify infrastructure needs early
- Secure independent research
- Make sure publishing is not constrained
- Assign clear roles and responsibilities
- Build a small network within the firm
- Stay in touch with the firm throughout the analysis phase
- Document data preparation steps and processes

What NOT to do

- Delay legal conversations
- Overpromise deliverables
- Assume data will arrive promptly and is ready to use
- Share the data with other parties
- Assume common understanding of timelines
- Ignore firm's preferences on publication visibility
- Fail to regularly update the firm

also provide continuity in case key employees leave or change roles. A broader network reduces dependency on a single point of contact and strengthens the institutional foundation for long-term collaboration. Such practices not only help to signal credibility and reliability but also lay the groundwork for sustained and successful future collaboration.

It is also essential to align on all deliverables and corresponding timelines, especially if outputs beyond the academic article are anticipated, such as internal reports, joint press releases, or presentations.

Legal aspects

An even more crucial point is to keep in mind legal aspects of the collaboration. A core component of the collaboration involves drafting and signing a Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) or a broader cooperation agreement with input from both the legal teams of the cooperation and the academic institution. This agreement should clearly outline the responsibilities of both parties regarding data usage and data security. It should also address the publication and use of research data, including citation obligations and usage rights, while safeguarding academic freedom and ensuring adherence to principles of good scientific practice.

Further legal considerations include:

- Whether and how data can be shared with journal editors during the review process
- Rights related to archiving the data for at least ten years
- Naming the company in the publication and determining if the company wishes to review the manuscript before publication
- Securing independent research and ensuring no constraints on publishing the manuscript.
- Financing potential costs for data extraction and data processing – on the firm's and on the researcher's side.

Note that these aspects may require negotiation and refinement during the collaboration setup.⁶

Data Management

Efficient data handling processes must be clearly defined, including how the data is shared, where it is stored, and who can access it under what conditions. Special care and additional safeguards must be implemented if personalized data subject to the GDPR is involved.⁷

⁶ Templates for NDAs and agreements are provided by several institutions (e.g., DFG <https://www.dfg.de/resource/blob/167850/41-026-en.rtf>). Although they mostly focus on joint industrial research, they can serve as a starting point for developing a data collaboration agreement.

⁷ For more information, see https://www.konsortswd.de/wp-content/uploads/RatSWD_Output8.6_Data-Protection-Guide.pdf

Technical infrastructure requirements should be addressed early. Under no circumstances should the data be shared with third parties without the firm's specific consent or a corresponding contractual amendment.

Various models of data provision exist. In some cases, the data is transferred directly to the researcher. Alternatively, the data may remain within the firm, with the researcher granted access, either on-site or remotely via a company laptop, often formalized through a contractual agreement. A third option involves the use of a RDC, which functions as a data host or intermediary infrastructure. In all cases, responsibilities for data delivery and updates should be clearly defined.

Moreover, researchers are advised to prepare comprehensive documentation (e.g. data management plans, codebooks) of the data processing steps. This not only contributes to a sustainable data foundation but also ensures data quality, transparency, and reproducibility over time.

Finally, it is crucial to identify a knowledgeable contact who can provide context about how the data was generated. Based on prior interviews, individuals from the business side often provide more useful insights than purely technical data contacts.

3.4. Managing the Collaboration Over Time: Long-Term Success

From One-Time Exchange to Long-Term Partnership

Once the framework for a data collaboration has been established and the first data exchange has been successfully completed, the cooperating parties decide how they want to shape and maintain the collaboration in the long term. In some cases, a one-time data exchange may be the most practical option for both sides. In other cases, there may be compelling reasons to pursue a long-term collaboration. Sustainable, trust-based partnerships with a long-term perspective and scalability can yield deeper insights, facilitate the integration of scientific methods into business practices, and provide researchers with access to unique data and expertise. Each cooperation should be tailored to the specific needs of both the researchers and the company involved. Key success factors for developing and evolving such collaborations include clear communication, effective coordination, and mutual trust.

Building the Foundations of Sustainable Collaboration

Ideally, the partners align long-term goals at the beginning of the collaboration. For researchers, a key objective might be the creation of a longitudinal dataset, data collected at regular intervals, or the opportunity to conduct follow-up studies building on an initial project. For companies, the focus might be on receiving regular, publicly visible reports or insights that inform strategic decisions. Establishing a data cooperation and developing a novel dataset typically requires significant time and effort. Continuing the collaboration enables both parties to leverage synergies and generate additional value. A well-structured data exchange process, along with thorough documentation of data preparation steps, provides the foundation for a sustainable collaboration. These practices not only enhance transparency but also reduce effort

for future data exchanges. Ongoing strategic refinement, supported by clearly defined milestones, can help ensure continued progress and lasting impact.

Communication, Trust, and Continuity

Clear communication, mutual trust, and a forward-looking mindset are essential for sustaining firm collaborations over time. At the operational level, roles, responsibilities, and communication channels should be clearly defined from the beginning. Partners should agree on when, how often, and through which formats (e.g., meetings, update reports, digital platforms) they will stay in contact. Regular check-ins can facilitate knowledge exchange and help address relevant developments, such as changes in the data-generating process, organizational changes that might impact the collaboration, or new insights arising from research analyses.

The importance of identifying an internal champion and cultivating a broader network within the firm has already been discussed in previous sections. However, interviewees highlighted an additional point relevant for ensuring a successful long-term collaboration. Champions often lack formal incentives to drive the collaboration forward. Researchers can support their

Managing the Collaboration Over Time

What to do

- Align long-term goals early
- Stick to agreed deliverables and deadlines
- Keep communication frequent and proactive, not just reactive
- Recognize and credit internal champions for their contributions
- Share knowledge frequently to reduce key-person risk
- Adapt collaboration to evolving interests and capacity
- Think through “what if” scenarios and remain flexible

What NOT to do

- Delay legal conversations
- Let communication fade after initial data delivery
- Rely on only one firm contact for continuity
- Ignore signs of organizational change at the firm
- Treat the collaboration as static rather than evolving
- Delay updates until problems arise
- Delay to document critical steps or decisions
- React rigidly when faced with unexpected changes

continued engagement by ensuring their efforts are made visible internally, by crediting their role in presentations and internal meetings. Recognizing the champion's contribution can improve their standing within the organization and reinforce their motivation, strengthening the relationship in the long run.

Personnel changes, organizational restructuring, or changing data infrastructure can disrupt even the most promising projects. Although formal contingency planning is rare in academic-industry partnerships, a forward-looking mindset is essential for ensuring continuity. Researchers and firms alike should be prepared for unexpected developments, whether a delayed data delivery, a change in staff, or stalled internal approvals. Good documentation practices and knowledge sharing routines can help protect the project from these risks. Regular meetings and proactive updates also contribute to a resilient collaboration over time, fostering trust and alignment. Thinking through possible scenarios in advance, staying responsive, and remaining adaptable can make it easier to navigate challenges when things do not go according to plan.

3.5. Ending a Collaboration

It goes without saying that the initiation and management of a cooperation should be carefully planned. Equally important, however, is to agree on how the collaboration will eventually be concluded, including any potential early exits.

Successful Completion of the Collaboration

There are different scenarios why a cooperation might end, the most straightforward being the successful achievement of its objectives. In such cases, all parties should agree on the steps toward a mutually successful completion. It is important to establish clear procedures for the handover of all relevant documents, data, and knowledge. All parties should agree on the terms of subsequent data storage and usage rights, ideally already clarified within the NDA or cooperation agreement.

Structured Exit Strategies

Nonetheless, there can be valid reasons for ending a cooperation at any stage. In these situations, it is crucial for the parties involved to manage a structured exit. For researchers, this might mean securing ongoing rights to use data that has already been exchanged. For companies, it could involve protecting the knowledge, competencies, or outputs generated during the cooperation. Ideally, contracts should include provisions for potential exit scenarios and related agreements.

Closing a Partnership and Building Future Opportunities

Most importantly, regardless of whether the cooperation was ultimately successful, all parties have likely invested significant time and effort. It is therefore important to end a cooperation on a respectful and collaborative note. The scientific community should bear in mind that future researchers may wish to collaborate with the company. It is essential to ensure that all sensitive

and proprietary information shared during the cooperation remains protected and confidential even after the collaboration has concluded. Appropriate measures and agreements should be put in place to safeguard this information from unauthorized disclosure or use. Ideally, the cooperation agreement specifies who has access to exchanged information and communications, how the data is stored and used during the collaboration, and how it is handled after the partnership ends. If this is not the case, the partners involved should formalize a supplemental agreement on the matter. Incorporating a joint review at the end of the cooperation can be highly valuable and can help to improve the effectiveness of future collaborations.

Ending a Collaboration

What to do

- Plan early for how the collaboration will end
- Ensure a structured handover of data, documents and insights
- Clarify rights to already exchanged data
- Protect confidentiality after project end
- Conduct a joint review of the collaboration
- Leave the door open for future partnerships

What NOT to do

- Neglect to secure ongoing rights to use shared data
- Avoid discussing how proprietary information is protected post-collaboration
- Disregard the value of maintaining a positive relationship
- Skip internal documentation at project close

4. Advancing Firm Data Access: Contributions from RDCs and Beyond

So far, the handbook has focused on how individual researchers can navigate the complexities of initiating and building collaborations with firms. However, institutional infrastructure can play an important role in enabling success. Research Data Centers, in particular, act as valuable intermediaries in data collaborations, helping build trust and supporting researchers across the entire lifecycle of a collaboration.

The empirical research landscape in Germany has been significantly strengthened through the establishment of various RDCs. These centers play a central role in providing researchers with access to high-quality, often sensitive data for scientific use. Their core tasks include preparing and documenting standardized data products according to the FAIR principles, providing and archiving datasets, and managing data use agreements. RDCs are accredited and regularly monitored by the German Data Forum (RatSWD) for these activities.

Data provided by RDCs can generally be categorized into three types of data products: (1) data derived from legal mandates and administrative registers (by RDCs in statistical offices), (2) data collected directly by researchers or research institutes (such as the ifo Business Surveys or the SOEP from DIW), and (3) data made accessible through collaborations between RDCs and private firms.

Well-established RDCs like the FDZ Ruhr at RWI and the LMU-ifo Economics & Business Data Center (EBDC) at the ifo Institute have shown how such collaborations can work in practice, as described in *Box 1* and *Box 2*. While the specific operating models of individual RDCs differ, their shared contribution lies in unlocking sensitive data for science while maintaining legal, technical and ethical safeguards. The experiences from FDZ Ruhr and the EBDC illustrate how institutional structures can support broader access to firm data, foster trust, and ensure high-quality empirical research.

From these experiences, several key insights emerge. RDCs offer legal and technical expertise, trusted infrastructure, and institutional credibility, reducing the risks associated with data sharing. They also provide continuity and stability in research environments often shaped by short-term contracts and shifting personnel. For firms, working with an RDC, a permanent institution, means not having to renegotiate every collaboration from scratch, making partnerships more scalable and sustainable over a longer period of time.

Therefore, RDCs play a crucial role in unlocking firm data for scientific research. Their work not only improves data availability but also strengthens the overall research infrastructure in Germany. Through their strategic partnerships and institutional stability, they are well-positioned to continue advancing empirical economic research for years to come and hence to give advice to others who seek to establish firm data collaborations on their own.

However, this handbook complements several ongoing initiatives in Germany and internationally that aim to foster data collaborations between firms and researchers. The following non-exhaustive overview provides additional guidance, advice and inspiration from long-standing examples of successful infrastructure and partnership models.

Additional Resources

“How-To” Resources

- The interdisciplinary section “Industry Engagement” of the **National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)** aims to systematically strengthen collaboration between science and industry by establishing a coordinated framework for cross-consortia partnerships, thereby unlocking new societal value through shared platforms, harmonized cooperation models, and the integration of economic stakeholders into the national research data infrastructure. For more info, see: <https://www.nfdi.de/section-industry-engagement/?lang=en>.
- The **Abdul Latif Jameel Poverty Action Lab (J-PAL)** is a global research center working to reduce poverty by ensuring that policy is informed by scientific evidence. It focusses especially on randomized control trials and field experiments in or with public institutions or firms, for which they provide a great step by step toolkit: <https://www.povertyactionlab.org/research-resources?view=toc#choose-a-view>.

Other Initiatives for Accessing Firm Data

(enablers, funding bodies, marketplaces)

- The **Data-Group Business 2 Science** initiative by the Stifterverband aims to pioneer cross-sectoral data sharing between academia and industry, actively shaping and advancing the (re)use of data through practical guidance, networking between stakeholders and political engagement to strengthen Germany’s overall data ecosystem. More info at <https://www.stifterverband.org/data-group>.
- The NFDI consortium **BERD@NFDI** develops research data infrastructure to support social scientists in managing and analyzing unstructured data throughout the research lifecycle. It offers a secure data marketplace where firms can provide their data and be matched with researchers. More info at: <https://www.berd-nfdi.de/research-data-marketplace/>.
- The **German Research Foundation (DFG)** launched an initiative in 2024 in order to identify needs and develop a dedicated funding scheme for research data collaborations between science and industry which is expected to start end of 2025. More info at: <https://www.dfg.de/de/aktuelles/neuigkeiten-themen/info-wissenschaft/2024/ifw-24-81>.
- The **revised European Regulation (EC) No 223/2009** will make privately held data available for official statistics.
- The **Predictive People Analytics initiative (PPA)** led by economists at the LMU Munich serves as a knowledge hub that brings together firms and researchers to advance evidence-based human resource management and organizational economics. See: <https://www.predictive-people-analytics.net/>.
- The CESifo cluster “**Research with firm data**” strives to connect researchers working with (big) data from firms and share best practices on research and collaborations with firms. More info at: <https://www.ifo.de/en/cesifo/cesifo-cluster>.
- Often researchers from various disciplines at universities invite firms directly to collaborate. See, for instance, the **Statistical Consulting Unit (StaBLab)** of the Department of Statistics at the LMU Munich (<https://www.stablab.stat.uni-muenchen.de/index.html>) or the **Chair for Quantitative Marketing** at the University of Mannheim (<https://www.bwl.uni-mannheim.de/quantitativemarketing/kooperationen/>).
- There are several academic institutions which have created commercial platforms and marketplaces where researchers can acquire firm data. Two examples include the **Wharton Research Data Services (WRDS)**, <https://wrds-www.wharton.upenn.edu/>) and **Kilts Center for Marketing** (<https://www.chicagobooth.edu/research/kilts/research-data>).

Notable Examples of Firm Data Collaborations in Research

- The **Opportunity Insights Economic Tracker** at Harvard University is a prime example of a visual platform that leverages data from collaborating firms to help stakeholders in policy and administration to make more informed decisions. See: <https://www.tracktherecovery.org/>.
- The **HBS Pricing Lab** collaborates with companies who share access to their proprietary datasets to study firm-level pricing decisions and capabilities to understand their micro and macroeconomic impacts. See: <https://www.pricinglab.org/>.
- “**Experimental Statistics**” are initiatives by (inter-)national statistical offices that use new data sources and methods, often provided by or developed in collaboration with firms. See, for example, the case of the **German Federal Statistical Office (DESTATIS)** at: https://www.destatis.de/EN/Service/EXSTAT/_node.html.

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KonsortSWD, as part of the National Research Data Infrastructure, is expanding offerings to support research with data in the social, behavioral, educational, and economic sciences. Our mission is to strengthen, expand and deepen the research data infrastructure for the study of society. It should be user-oriented and consider the needs of the research communities. An important cornerstone is the network of research data centers that has been built up for more than two decades by the German Data Forum (RatSWD).

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